

A Case Study of Changes in Assessment at University Level

Ann O'Shea

Department of Mathematics and Statistics, Maynooth University

The COVID-19 pandemic necessitated major changes in assessment in university mathematics courses. In this paper, I will use Lithner's Reasoning Framework to analyse tasks from three instances of the same advanced calculus module from the years 2019, 2020, and 2021. The tasks from the years in question have been classified into those that require creative mathematical reasoning and those that can be solved using imitative reasoning. I investigate whether the opportunities for creative reasoning offered to students in this module changed significantly during the pandemic, and consider the implications of the move to e-assessment.

Keywords: advanced calculus, mathematical reasoning, tasks, e-assessment

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic had obvious short-term implications for university level mathematics education in Ireland (O'Shea, 2022). Traditional in-person final examinations were an early casualty in 2020; and research was carried out on lecturers' and students' views of the move to online assessment (Ní Fhloinn & Fitzmaurice, 2021a; Meehan & Howard 2020). Since then most final examinations have returned to their usual format; however, in the case of continuous assessment it seems as if the use of online quizzes and pdf upload assignments remains very common. The move to e-assessment is not new, but the pandemic certainly accelerated the change. Kinnear et al. (2022) recognise the need for research in this area and have developed a research agenda for e-assessment in undergraduate mathematics courses. One area of research identified is that of the capabilities of e-assessment, and in particular on the types of reasoning and understanding that can be fostered and measured using online assessment. Kinnear et al. (2022) note that researchers have analysed tasks used in traditional assessments but that very little analysis of this sort has been done in the area of e-assessment.

Studies have shown (Boesen et al., 2010; Jonsson et al., 2014) that the types of tasks assigned to students can affect their learning; and the use of tasks with lower levels of cognitive demand leads to rote-learning by students and a consequent inability to solve unfamiliar problems or to transfer knowledge to other areas competently and appropriately. De Guzman et al. (1998) advised university instructors to design problems that target the type of thinking they themselves value, and to resist assigning purely technical exercises, in order to help students appreciate the type of mathematical thinking required at university. It makes sense then, to investigate what kind of questions are used in undergraduate mathematics assessments. Some studies have been carried out on the types of tasks used in calculus courses at university level. In Sweden, Bergqvist (2007) analysed examination questions from 16 first-year calculus courses at four universities. She found that the majority of the examination questions (70%) could be solved using imitative reasoning alone, and that all but one of the examinations could be passed in this way. In Ireland, Mac an Bhaird et al. (2017) found that nearly 90% of graded tasks in non-specialist calculus courses could be solved with imitative

reasoning, while in a specialist course the proportion was 36%. Note that both of these studies use Lithner's Reasoning Framework (Lithner, 2008) to classify the tasks, and neither focus on e-assessment.

In this case study, I will use Lithner's framework to classify tasks from three instances of an advanced calculus module taught in the Spring of the years 2019, 2020, and 2021. In that period, changes necessitated by the pandemic lockdowns meant that the continuous assessment for this module moved from hand-written assignments graded by tutors to online automatically graded quizzes and pdf uploads. The research questions for this study are:

RQ1: Are there differences in the proportions of creative reasoning tasks used in the three instances of this module?

RQ2: If we consider graded tasks only, is there a difference in the proportion of creative reasoning tasks between the three years?

RQ3: Is there a difference in the proportion of creative reasoning tasks between automatically graded quizzes and tutor-graded homework?

Theoretical Framework

The analysis of tasks in this paper is based on Lithner's Reasoning Framework (Lithner 2008). Lithner defines reasoning as 'the line of thought adopted to produce assertions and reach conclusions in task-solving' (Lithner 2008, p 257). This definition could apply to a wide range of student work from routine calculations to sophisticated proofs. He distinguishes between *imitative* and *creative reasoning*. Imitative reasoning (IR) has two main types: memorised and algorithmic. Memorised reasoning is characterised as

The strategy choice is founded on recalling a complete answer. The strategy implementation consists only of writing it down. (Lithner 2008, p258)

While algorithmic reasoning is characterised as

The strategy choice is to recall a solution algorithm. The remaining reasoning parts of the strategy implementation are trivial for the reasoner, only a careless mistake can prevent an answer from being reached. (Lithner 2008, p259)

In contrast, Lithner defines creative reasoning (CR) as having the following three properties:

Novelty - A new (to the reasoner) reasoning sequence is created, or a forgotten one is re-created. Plausibility - There are arguments supporting the strategy choice and/or strategy implementation motivating why the conclusions are true or plausible. Mathematical foundation - The arguments are anchored in intrinsic mathematical properties of the components involved in the reasoning. (Lithner 2008, p 266).

The notes and other teaching resources available to students in the module in question informed the classification of the assessment tasks into the IR and CR categories.

Methodology

This paper is a case study which explores the changes in assessment over a three year period in a single module. We use Stakes's (2000) definition of different categories of case

study, namely intrinsic, instrumental, and collective. In an intrinsic case study, the analysis focusses on a particular single case and no attempt is made to generalise about larger phenomena. Thus, this paper is an intrinsic case study, and the case is the continuous assessment in the MT202A module in Maynooth University.

The Module

I analysed the tasks associated with the course MT202A over the three years 2019, 2020, 2021. This module was delivered in the Spring semester of these years. The module is the fourth calculus module taken by students in the Mathematical Studies programme, and covers the topics of infinite series, multiple integrals and line integrals. I did not analyse tasks which appeared on midterm or final examinations.

In 2019, the module was taught in person with 23 lectures and five tutorials. There were five hand-in assignments (consisting of five or six tasks each) which were graded by a tutor, as well as practice problems for the students to work on at home or in tutorials. The assignments were worth 15% of the module mark, and tutorials took place after the hand-in dates.

In 2020, the module was scheduled to run as in 2019. It did so for the first six weeks of the semester but the COVID-19 pandemic meant that all teaching went online in March 2020. The final six weeks of the module took place during lockdown. Lectures were replaced with a suite of short videos and online notes. The hand-in assignments were replaced by pdf uploads which consisted of a single task each time. In addition, there were two multiple choice quizzes on the VLE (Moodle). Tutorials were replaced with online sessions on Teams. The assignments were worth 15% of the module mark and the quizzes were worth 10%.

In 2021, teaching remained online. The lectures were replaced by a suite of short videos supplemented by a class meeting once every second week on Teams. In these meetings, the lecturer summarized the main ideas and did some worked examples. The tutorials took place on Teams before the assignment deadlines; tutors and students worked through a set of tutorial problems. The assignments were replaced with four Moodle quizzes (designed using STACK) and one pdf upload assignment (which was graded by a tutor). There were also four practice quizzes, five sets of practice problems, and five sets of tutorial problems. The graded quizzes and the pdf upload together were worth 15% of the final grade.

In each of the three years, the lecturer assigned a small number of optional problems. These were aimed at high achieving students and usually required them to construct proofs.

The Analysis

To begin with, I gathered all tasks used in each iteration of the module. I created an SPSS file which listed each task, along with the year, the grading status (graded, optional, practice), the type of assessment (quiz, homework sheet, tutorial problems, practice sheet, practice quiz) and the medium of assessment (online quiz, on paper, pdf upload). For each task, I used the definitions of IR and CR above along with the resources available to the

students to decide on the classification. I recorded both the reasoning classification and the reason for this in the data file.

Results

Number of Tasks

Let us first look at the number of tasks in the module in each of the three years. It is clear from Table 1 that the number of tasks increased in 2021, in fact there were more than twice the number of tasks associated with the 2021 instance of the module than were offered in the two previous years. This difference is statistically significant (chi-Square Test, $n=469$, $dof=2$, $\chi = 82.712$, $p < 0.001$).

This difference is not a surprise, since, as we outlined above, each assignment in 2021 had an associated practice quiz and practice sheet plus a tutorial sheet. In fact, the numbers of graded questions in each of the three years were very similar (43 in 2019, 39 in 2020, and 41 in 2021) but the number of practice questions increased dramatically (67 in 2019, 61 in 2020, and 201 in 2021). Grading status is not independent of year with a much higher proportion of practice questions in 2021 than in the other two years (Fisher exact test, $p < 0.001$).

Table 1

Classification of graded, practice and optional questions

Year	Grading Status	Imitative Reasoning	Creative Reasoning	Total
2019	Graded	29 (67.4%)	14 (32.6%)	43
	Practice	50 (74.6%)	17 (25.4%)	67
	Optional	0 (0%)	5 (100%)	5
	2019 Total	79 (68.7%)	36 (31.3%)	115
2020	Graded	33 (84.6%)	6 (15.4%)	39
	Practice	47 (77%)	14 (23%)	61
	Optional	0 (0%)	5 (100%)	5
	2020 Total	80 (76.2%)	25 (23.8%)	105
2021	Graded	32 (78%)	9 (22%)	41
	Practice	167 (83.1%)	34 (16.9%)	201
	Optional	3 (42.9%)	4 (57.1%)	7
	2021 Total	202 (81.1%)	47 (18.9%)	249
Total		361 (77%)	108 (23%)	469

Proportions of Imitative and Creative Reasoning Tasks

We can see from Table 1 that the proportion of CR tasks has decreased each time the module was run (from 31.3% in 2019 to 23.8% in 2020 and 18.9% in 2021). This difference is statistically significant as the classification of a task is not independent from the year (chi-

square test, $n=469$, $dof=2$, $\chi=6.903$, $p=0.032$). We see that there is a statistically significant higher proportion of IR tasks in 2021 compared to the other two years. We will endeavour to investigate the reason for this difference. It would be tempting to say that the move away from written homework assignments to online quizzes could be the reason.

Proportions of Imitative and Creative Reasoning Tasks amongst Graded Tasks

If we look at graded tasks only (Table 2), we do not see a statistically significant difference in the proportion of CR tasks between the three years (chi-square test, $n=123$, $dof=2$, $\chi=3.438$, $p=0.173$). We see that the biggest proportion of CR tasks in the graded assignments occurred in 2019 with the smallest in 2020.

Recall that in 2019, the graded tasks were all submitted homework tasks while in 2021 the majority came from graded quizzes. We investigated whether there is a difference in the proportion of IR tasks between tutor-graded homeworks and automatically graded quizzes (Table 2). The analysis shows that there is not a statistically significant difference between graded homework and graded quizzes. This is the case for all years combined (Fisher exact test, $p=0.216$), as well as each of the years 2020 (Fisher exact test, $p=0.296$) and 2021 (Fisher exact test, $p=0.299$). However note that in 2021, 40% of the pdf upload homework was classified as CR as opposed to only 19.4% of the Moodle quiz tasks.

Table 2

Classification of graded tasks by assessment type

Year	Assessment Type	Imitative Reasoning	Creative Reasoning	Total
2019	On Paper	29 (67.4%)	14 (32.6%)	43
	PDF Upload	-	-	-
	Moodle Quiz	-	-	-
	2019 Total	29 (67.4%)	14 (32.6%)	43
2020	On Paper	20 (80%)	5 (20%)	25
	PDF Upload	3 (75%)	1 (25%)	4
	Moodle Quiz	10 (100%)	0 (0%)	10
	2020 Total	33 (84.6%)	6 (15.4%)	39
2021	On paper	-	-	-
	PDF Upload	3 (60%)	2 (40%)	5
	Moodle Quiz	29 (80.6%)	7 (19.4%)	36
	2021 Total	32 (78%)	9 (22%)	41
Total		94 (76.4%)	29 (23.6%)	123

If we combine paper and pdf upload then overall the classification is independent of the mode of assessment (chi-square test, $n=123$, $\chi=2.8501$, $p=0.091$). Therefore, we have not

found significant differences in the classification of the tasks on graded written assignments (whether they are submitted in hard copy or via pdf upload) and those on graded quizzes.

Comparison of Practice and Graded Tasks

If we look at all three years together, then grading status is not independent of the reasoning classification (Fisher exact test, $n=469$, $p<0.001$) and this is also true if we look at each year separately. We see (Table 1) that the optional questions have a very high proportion of CR questions while the practice questions have a high proportion of IR questions. However, if we do not consider the optional questions at all and only include practice and graded tasks, then the reasoning classification is independent of the type of task (that is graded or practice). This is true in each year separately and overall.

Recall that the graded questions comprised written assignments and Moodle quizzes, and that the practice questions are taken from practice sheets, practice quizzes, tutorial questions and practice questions on the written assignment sheets. Looking at 2021 only (Table 3), we see that the practice sheets have the highest proportion of IR questions amongst the assessment types, but the differences are not statistically significant (Fisher exact test, $p=0.179$). However, if we combine all of the tasks which are not on practice sheets and compare them with the practice sheet tasks, then the proportion of practice sheet tasks that were classified as IR was significantly higher (chi-square test, $n=249$, $\chi= 4.6057$, $p=0.0319$).

Table 3

Classification of the 2021 tasks

Assessment Type	Imitative Reasoning	Creative Reasoning	Total
Homework Sheet	17 (70.8%)	7 (29.2%)	24
Graded Quiz	29 (80.6%)	7 (19.4%)	36
Tutorial Sheet	36 (78.3%)	10 (21.7%)	46
Practice Sheet	95 (87.2%)	14 (12.8%)	109
Practice Quiz	25 (80%)	5 (20%)	25
Total	25 (73.5%)	9 (26.5%)	34

Discussion

In answer to the first research question, the task analysis has revealed significant differences between the proportions of IR/CR tasks in the three instances of the module. The proportion of CR tasks was not very large in any of the three years, although higher than corresponding modules in the Mac an Bhaird et al. (2017) study. We have seen that the proportion of CR tasks in MT202A has decreased during the pandemic. It would be tempting to conclude that the decrease was related to the move to e-assessment but when considering graded questions alone the difference between the years was not significant (RQ2). In particular, the quiz questions do not seem to have caused the decrease in the proportion of CR

questions. There was not sufficient evidence for a significant difference in the proportion of CR tasks between automatically graded quizzes and tutor-graded assignments (RQ3).

We did see that there was a significant increase in numbers of tasks in 2021, largely as a result of structural changes which meant more practice questions, practice quizzes and tutorial problems. The analysis showed that the main source of IR tasks in 2021 were the practice sheets. These were designed in an effort to provide resources and support to students when they had no face-to-face teaching in lectures, tutorials or the Mathematics Support Centre. However, on reflection, these sheets may have been counterproductive given their lack of creative reasoning tasks (Jonsson et al., 2014), and it is possible that the large number of questions was overwhelming for students.

The extra work for the lecturer in designing these tasks and providing solutions should also be taken into consideration. Recall that the number of tasks in the module doubled in 2021. This, along with the work involved in preparing 1081 minutes of online instruction (766 minutes of video and 315 minutes of recap classes on Teams) for this module as opposed to the usual 1150 (i.e. 23x50) minutes of face-to-face lectures, represents a considerable increase in workload for the lecturer. It may explain why lecturers reported that teaching online during the pandemic was very time-consuming and stressful (Ní Fhloinn & Fitzmaurice, 2021b).

This current study clearly has limitations: it concerns just one module and one task-designer. It would be useful to extend the study to a range of modules to investigate the effect that the changes made in response to the pandemic had on reasoning opportunities in undergraduate mathematics assessments. It would also be prudent to investigate further how the move to e-assessment is likely to affect the provision of these reasoning opportunities in the future.

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